

X-Ray Diffractogram- SAIF Kochi

Sample 1 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

2Theta

Parent	2Theta
Sample ID	Sample 1
File Name	SAIFXR3892-220509-01(5LZA).raw (Smooth)
Scan Type	Coupled TwoTheta/Theta
Scan Mode	Continuousscan
Scan Status	Completed
Start	10.000 °
End	80.007 °
Step Size	0.020 °
Total Time/Step	57.60 s
Temperature	25 °C (Room)
Goniometer Radius	200.5 mm
2-theta	10.000 °
Theta	5.000 °
Sample Rotation	15.000 1/min
Anode	Cu
ka1	1.54060 Å
ka2	1.54439 Å
ka2 Ratio	0.50000
kβ	1.39222 Å
Wavelength for display	1.54060 Å
Generator kV	40.0 kV
Generator mA	35.0 mA
Detector Name	LynxEye
Detector Opening	2.945 °
Primary Soller slit	2.500 °
Secondary Soller slit	2.500 °
Air-Scatter Screen Mode	Automatic
Divergence Slit	15.000 mm
Antiscatter Slit	18.000
Slit Mode	Variable
Y-Scale Factor	1
Curvature	1.000
Compute Crystallinity	No
Crystallinity - From	10.000
Crystallinity - To	80.007
%-Crystallinity	
%-Amorphous	
Global Area	
Reduced Area	
Operator Name	Lab Manager
Creation Date/Time	6/4/2022 12:35:33 PM
Last Write Date/Time	6/4/2022 12:35:33 PM
Measurement Duration	2.06:45:07
Application Type	PowderDiffraction